

KEY ISSUES OF IMPLEMENTATION OF MODERN INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IN MANUFACTURING ENTERPRISES

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Abstract. *This article is devoted to improving the functions and principles of ICT implementation in enterprises. Developed practical recommendations and proposals for the implementation and improvement of the use of information and communication technologies in enterprises of the country.*

Keywords: *information, technology, function, tamoil, information technology, communication, enterprise, development, introduction, country, management.*

Introduction

Today, no one can even imagine the development of manufacturing enterprises without modern information technologies. Because information and communication technologies are currently developing rapidly, which imposes on manufacturing enterprises the task of introducing new innovative equipment and technologies into their activities and increasing their competitiveness using high technologies. The concept of introducing "Smart City" technologies has been adopted in our country, according to which projects such as "smart transport", "smart education", "smart medicine", "smart energy system", "smart construction", "smart utilities", "smart home", "smart government", "smart neighborhood" have been identified as the main directions of introducing "Smart City" technologies. At the same time, a number of problems remain in the implementation of ICT in most enterprises of our country. Great attention is also paid to this in the program for the implementation of the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the Year of Active Investments and Social Development.

The modern development and achievements of information technologies indicate the need for informatization of all spheres of science and human activity. Informatization of society is understood as the use of information as a social asset that ensures the development of the economy, the scientific and technological development of the country, the acceleration of the processes of democratization and intellectualization of society. The main tasks of modern information technologies for enterprise management are to solve various problems of searching for, collecting, processing, storing the necessary information, developing and optimizing new information. The task is carried out not only by selecting and automating time-consuming, regularly repeated, data processing operations, but also by processing them to obtain new information necessary for making effective management decisions.

Over the past decade, information and communication technologies have significantly improved the management of enterprises, as they provide managers and heads of enterprises at all levels with the latest methods of processing and analyzing economic and social information necessary for making the best and most alternative management decisions. Nowadays, information

and communication technologies are one of the main components of economic development. Almost all firms and consumers are increasingly using computers and the Internet for economic purposes, such as providing consumers with more diversified and customized products, improving product quality, and selling goods and services. As we all know, the expansion of information and communication technologies in developed and developing countries and their impact on economic growth has been growing rapidly over the past two decades.

However, within-country data on computer, mobile phone and Internet users reflect different rates of ICT penetration across countries and regions, and despite the recent global economic crisis, ICT usage has shown an increasing trend. In fact, information and communication technologies are the integration of electronics, telecommunications, software, networks, decentralized computer workstations and mass media, all of which have a significant impact on firms, industry and the economy as a whole. Information and communication technologies consist of various "communication equipment", including radio, television, communication equipment and software. Therefore, investments in the information and communication sector are mainly made in computers and telecommunications, software and services. Information systems and technologies are increasingly being used in various areas of human activity from year to year. The purpose of their creation, implementation and widespread use is to solve the problems of informatization of society and all human activities. Informatization of society is understood as the implementation of comprehensive measures aimed at ensuring full and timely access to enriched knowledge and reliable information in all socially significant areas of human activity.

This means that the widespread implementation of modern information systems and technologies increases the effectiveness of decisions made. This will ensure not only the growth of economic indicators of the development of the national economy, but also the achievement of qualitative scientific achievements in fundamental and applied sciences aimed at the development of production, the creation of new jobs, the improvement of the living standards of the population, and environmental protection. In the new 21st century, the national economy of countries is becoming globalized and is becoming an information economy. That is, the role of information and knowledge in the national economy is increasing and they have become a strategic resource. 90% of the information and knowledge accumulated in the world has been created over the past 30 years. The daily increase in the volume of information and knowledge requires the effective use of information and communication technologies on a large scale in all sectors of the national economy, including education.

Information has become a resource that can be searched and distributed, just like traditional resources. There is serious reason to say that the total volume of this resource used will determine the strategic potential of states in the future, as well as their defense capabilities. In the rational organization and use of information resources, they appear as the equivalent of labor, material and energy resources. At the moment, information is the only type of resource that helps to use all other resources wisely and efficiently and to preserve them. Thus, information resources are not only the main part of production in a modern information society, but also a commodity as a source of national income.

By the 21st century, for the first time in the history of mankind, information has become a tool of work in the production of industrialized countries. The tendency of labor resources from the sphere of material production to the sphere of information without any deviation is becoming more and more obvious. The main reason for this is that in the process of growth and development of production, the volume of information necessary for decision-making and management is

increasing. This growth is manifested, first of all, in economic, technical, scientific, technological and social systems and processes. Management errors associated with a lack of information are very costly. At the same time, the system that has the most information wins in terms of management and production efficiency, development and use of advanced technologies.

Experts, first of all, consider free access to information by economists to be one of the main conditions for the effectiveness of a market economy in the conditions of industrial development. The main areas of their activity and production of society are in one way or another connected with information, and they account for 40-60% of the employed. Information services account for 10% of the world's gross social product and national income. 90% of this falls on the share of the USA, Japan and Western Europe. Information is an important product of intellectual activity. In all industrially developed countries, the development and implementation of "methods and means" of delivering these products to their users is being carried out at a rapid pace, which is reflected in the creation of the information systems and technologies industry.

The emergence of the information technology industry depends on how they ensure the creation of an information society. The information technology industry produces information products and tools and delivers them to consumers. Information products are understood, first of all, as various fields of knowledge obtained by traditional means or with the help of electronic technology, as well as other forms of data and information. The mass production of personal computers has opened up wide opportunities, especially for the information technology industry. Personal computers have penetrated almost all areas of human activity and have expanded the possibilities of specialists to access the source of knowledge and participate in its direct processing. Information technology works both as an independent information processing system and as a functional component and provides management within a larger system.

Such systems include industrial enterprises, firms, corporations, financial-credit and commercial-trade organizations, automated management of production and economic processes, scientific experiments, economic-mathematical models, data processing systems, library services and a number of other areas. The education system in the world is developing at a rapid pace. For example, if we take the Netherlands, highly qualified graduates are unemployed. That is why we need to closely study the level of demand for the personnel we are providing. If there is no need for such personnel in our domestic market, we need to search for their demand in the external market via the Internet. It should be noted that 85% of professors at US universities are Indians.

Their achievement of these achievements can be explained, first of all, by their deep knowledge of exact sciences, perfect study of foreign languages, and the ability to effectively apply information and communication technologies in the national economy and education. Currently, not only in the field of education, but also in all sectors of the national economy, the Internet, e-commerce, e-business, virtual commerce, virtual education, distance learning, and virtual stand technologies are widely penetrating. Managing an enterprise with the help of information technologies requires a detailed analysis of the object, studying its management tasks and structure, as well as managing information flows. Based on the analysis of survey materials, an information management model was developed, which establishes the relationship between information processing tasks and new information flows.

The main principles of involving information and communication technologies in enterprises are as follows:

1. The principle of operational control (based on real-time management).

2. The principle of primary management (consists of collecting and analyzing data on the state of the controlled object, modeling and forecasting its state, planning control measures, providing direct support for making decisions on their implementation, presenting their solutions to executors and monitoring their timely implementation).

3. The principle of control taking into account the impact of changes in the external and internal environment on enterprises.

4. The principle of network management, which allows for the interconnection of vertical and horizontal communication lines and enterprise flows. It is characterized as a concept that includes information and communication technologies and other information equipment, as well as computer programs that cover computers, office equipment (cash registers, calculators), and communication equipment. In this article, we show the relationship between the use of information and communication technologies and the growth rate of GDP per capita in a number of countries around the world. Although many studies provide empirical evidence that ICT investment and economic growth are related, the study of the impact of ICT use on economic growth is still an underexplored area. The impact of ICT on economic growth has been analyzed by many authors in the last decade. Much of the evidence in this area confirms that the positive impact of ICT on economic growth does not appear before the mid-1990s.

Oliner and Sichel empirically compared the impact of high-level ICT on economic growth in the late 1990s, along with capital investments in computers, software, and telecommunications equipment, but they did not give positive results. According to research by Jorgenson and Stiroh in the 2000s, the contribution of ICT to the economic development of the United States was the replacement of computers, related equipment, and services resulting from technological change.

Conclusion

Thus, today, the penetration of ICT into all aspects of our lives is fundamentally changing the mechanisms for organizing the economy, vocational education, business, and continuing education. It should be noted that in the globalization of the world economy, the size of the labor market for offering educational services via the Internet is unlimited.

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